

ENERGY METHOD FOR BUCKLING OF CFRP INTERCONNECTED PLATES WITH ARBITRARY BOUNDARY CONDITIONS.

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ABSTRACT

The energy Rayleigh-Ritz method has been widely used for the determination of critical buckling loads of CFRP panels in the aeronautic industry, but the typical requirement of an approximate displacement function that pre-satisfies the boundary conditions has prevented the application of the method to more general structures where several interconnected panels are involved.

An energy method overcoming this limitation is presented in this paper. The proposed method is also based on the Rayleigh-Ritz approach, but instead of using a predefined displacement function satisfying automatically the boundary conditions, these are imposed as a set of linear equations in the unknown coefficients, transforming the problem of the total potential energy minimization into a conditional optimization that is solved using the well-known Lagrange multipliers method.

Thanks to the described development, the scope of applicability of previous implementations of the Rayleigh-Ritz method is enlarged, allowing the determination of the static deformation and buckling loads of structures that were only assessed before by means of Finite Element Models. In addition, the associated computation time reduction enables the method to be used for structural optimization.

The particular application of the method to the determination of the critical local buckling loads of CFRP stringers with arbitrary sections (including closed sections like omega stringers) is presented and compared against Finite Element Models results.

1 INTRODUCTION

Buckling is a key sizing driver on the design process of composite stiffened panels used in the aerospace industry. Consequently, a wide variety of methods have been developed to determine the critical buckling load of stiffened structures, ranging from simple closed form solutions to more sophisticated finite element methods.

Typically, when a structure is being sized, a compromise between performance and accuracy has to be reached. When the most accurate methods are used for sizing, the precision of the final solution is guaranteed but at the expense of a lower number of sizing loops, which could lead to an under optimized structure. On the other hand, using the best performing method usually implies a limited scope of applicability and/or neglecting some effects that, once considered, would imply a rework of the design solution to comply with the structural requirements.

The buckling method here proposed is applicable to a set of interconnected composite plates with definable boundary conditions, providing a good balance between the efficiency of the closed form solutions and the accuracy of finite element methods.

2 ANALYSIS DESCRIPTION

The method described on this paper can deal with any set of interconnected panels, provided that each single panel has a rectangular shape.

Each individual panel can be submitted to any combination of in-plane loads (longitudinal, transverse and shear) including in-plane bending and they may be stiffened by longitudinal and/or transverse stiffeners.

Panels can be made of any anisotropic layup, but they cannot exhibit internal changes of thickness, layup or material properties. However, this limitation can be easily overridden by splitting the panel in several uniform panels and assembling them.

The panels can be assembled at different angles, creating closed cross-sections or combinations including free edges.

2.1 Energy method

The principle of virtual work states that a continuous body is in equilibrium if and only if the virtual work of all forces, internal (δW_I) and external (δW_E), acting on the body is zero under a virtual displacement (Ref. 1)

$$\delta W = \delta W_I + \delta W_E = 0 \quad (1)$$

The virtual work done by actual body forces \vec{f} and surface forces \vec{t} in moving through the virtual displacement $\delta \vec{u}$ is:

$$\delta W_E = - \left(\int_{\Omega} \vec{f} \cdot \delta \vec{u} d\Omega + \int_S \vec{t} \cdot \delta \vec{u} dS \right) \quad (2)$$

and the total internal virtual work stored in the body is:

$$\delta W_I = \int_{\Omega} \sigma \cdot \delta \varepsilon \cdot d\Omega \quad (3)$$

For elastic bodies a strain density function u exists such that $\sigma = \frac{\partial u}{\partial \varepsilon}$, and the principle of virtual work can be transformed into a minimization problem known as the Principle of Minimum Total Potential Energy.

$$\begin{aligned} \delta W = 0 &= \underbrace{\int_{\Omega} \sigma \delta \varepsilon d\Omega}_{\delta W_I} - \underbrace{\left[\int_{\Omega} \vec{f} \cdot \delta \vec{u} d\Omega + \int_S \vec{t} \cdot \delta \vec{u} dS \right]}_{\delta W_E} = \\ &= \int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial u}{\partial \varepsilon} \delta \varepsilon d\Omega + \delta V = \delta U + \delta V = \delta(U + V) \equiv \delta \Pi \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The sum $U + V = \Pi$ is the total potential energy and the body is in equilibrium when the variation of this magnitude is null, reaching Π a minimum.

2.2 Rayleigh-Ritz approach

The Rayleigh-Ritz approach implies defining an approximate solution representing a displacement field that automatically complies with the boundary conditions, but in this case we are not imposing any restriction to this deflection shape function but, on the contrary, it is desirable that such deflection shape does not impose any restriction so that any possible boundary condition can be properly considered.

For the sake of simplicity, only the terms depending on the perpendicular displacements are retained on this paper (being the method extendable to all the degrees of freedom of the plates). The vertical displacements can be expressed as a function of a set of unknown coefficients c_i

$$w(x, y) = F(x, y, c_i) \quad (5)$$

Introducing this deflection shape function into the potential energy functional Π defined in the previous section a functional depending only on the solution unknowns c_i is obtained.

$$\Pi = \Pi(c_1, c_2, \dots, c_N) \quad (6)$$

The equilibrium of the structure is reached, according to the principle of minimum total potential energy, by obtaining the minimum of the functional Π with respect to the unknown coefficients:

$$\delta\Pi = 0 \Rightarrow \frac{\partial\Pi}{\partial c_i} = 0 \quad \forall i \quad (7)$$

As the structure considered is composed of several panels, a different deflection shape function consisting on a double Chebyshev series is defined for each panel k :

$$w^k = \sum_i \sum_j C_{ij} \cos(i\xi) \cos(j\eta) \quad (8)$$

where:

$$x = \frac{a^k}{2} (\cos(\xi) + 1) ; y = \frac{b^k}{2} (\cos(\eta) + 1) \quad (9)$$

The parameters a^k and b^k in the previous equations define the length and width of each panel respectively.

2.3 Boundary conditions

Structures must satisfy several different constraint conditions. In the standard Rayleigh-Ritz methods these boundary conditions are automatically fulfilled by the carefully chosen deflection functions, but in this case where the goal is to enable us to define various boundary conditions, these have to be imposed as a set of N_c linear equations that must be subsequently satisfied by the solution:

$$e_i(c_1, c_2, \dots, c_N) = d_i \quad \text{for } i = 1..N_c \quad (10)$$

The minimization problem becomes a conditional optimization that will be solved by means of the well-known Lagrange multipliers method.

The Lagrange multiplier method consists in multiplying each of these constraint equations with arbitrary parameters λ_i and adding the result to the minimum potential energy equation, obtaining a new objective function Π_2 :

$$\Pi_2 = \Pi + \sum \lambda_i \cdot e_i(c_1, c_2, \dots, c_N, d_i) \quad (11)$$

When the structure is composed by M interconnected panels, the modified total potential energy Π_2 has to be computed for the complete structure as the sum of the total potential energy of each individual panel in addition to the terms coming from the Lagrange multipliers method:

$$\Pi_2 = \sum_{i=1}^M U_i(c_1^i, \dots, c_N^i) + \sum_{i=1}^M V_i(c_1^i, \dots, c_N^i) + \sum_{i=1}^{N_c} \lambda_i e_i(c_1^1, \dots, c_N^1, \dots, c_1^M, \dots, c_N^M, d_i) \quad (12)$$

The expressions for U_i and V_i are quadratic in the coefficients c_j^i while the boundary conditions e_i are linear. Consequently the first derivatives of Π_2 together with the equations defining the boundary conditions provide a complete set of linear equations to obtain all these unknown coefficients.

$$\frac{\partial \Pi_2}{\partial c_j^i} = \sum_{i=1}^M \frac{\partial U_i}{\partial c_j^i} + \sum_{i=1}^M \frac{\partial V_i}{\partial c_j^i} + \sum_{i=1}^{N_c} \lambda_i \frac{\partial e_i}{\partial c_j^i} = 0 \quad \text{for } i = 1, \dots, M; j = 1, \dots, N \quad (13)$$

$$e_i(c_1^1, c_2^1, \dots, c_N^1, \dots, c_1^M, c_2^M, \dots, c_N^M) = d_i \quad \text{for } i = 1, \dots, N_c$$

The unknown coefficients of the approximate solutions together with the Lagrange multipliers λ_i can be obtained from the combined set of linear of equations coming from the minimization of the new functional and the imposed boundary conditions.

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \frac{\partial \Pi_2}{\partial c_i} = 0 \quad \text{for } i = 1 \dots N \\ e_j(c_1, c_2, \dots, c_N) = d_j \quad \text{for } j = 1 \dots N_c \end{array} \right\} \Rightarrow \begin{array}{l} c_i \quad \text{for } i = 1 \dots N \\ \lambda_j \quad \text{for } j = 1 \dots N_c \end{array} \quad (14)$$

Being the approximate displacement functions for the different panels independent each other, the previous system can be expressed as a block diagonal system:

$$\begin{bmatrix} [U]^1 & [0] & \dots & [0] \\ [0] & [U]^2 & \ddots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & [0] \\ [0] & \dots & [0] & [U]^N \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \{c\}^1 \\ \{c\}^2 \\ \vdots \\ \{c\}^N \end{Bmatrix} + \rho \begin{bmatrix} [V]^1 & [0] & \dots & [0] \\ [0] & [V]^2 & \ddots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & [0] \\ [0] & \dots & [0] & [V]^N \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \{c\}^1 \\ \{c\}^2 \\ \vdots \\ \{c\}^N \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} [C]^{1T} \\ [C]^{2T} \\ \vdots \\ [C]^{NT} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \lambda_1 \\ \vdots \\ \lambda_{N_c} \end{Bmatrix} = \{T\} \quad (15)$$

$$[[C]^1 [C]^2 \dots [C]^N] \begin{Bmatrix} \{c\}^1 \\ \{c\}^2 \\ \vdots \\ \{c\}^N \end{Bmatrix} = \{d\}$$

where the terms of each matrix can be obtained as:

$$U_{ij}^k = \frac{\partial^2 U^k}{\partial c_i^k \partial c_j^k}, \quad V_{ij}^k = \frac{\partial^2 V^k}{\partial c_i^k \partial c_j^k}, \quad C_{ij}^k = \frac{\partial e_i}{\partial c_j^k} \quad (16)$$

Some of the unknown coefficients will not be independent but can be derived from the relations imposed by the boundary conditions. To identify the dependent coefficients, the rectangular matrix $[C]$ used to define the restrictions can be transformed by reordering the unknown coefficients rewriting the set of equations as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} [U]_d & [U]_{id} \\ [U]_{di} & [U]_i \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \{c\}_d \\ \{c\}_i \end{Bmatrix} + \rho \begin{bmatrix} [V]_d & [V]_{id} \\ [V]_{di} & [V]_i \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \{c\}_d \\ \{c\}_i \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} [C]_d^T \\ [C]_i^T \end{bmatrix} \{\lambda\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \{T\}_d \\ \{T\}_i \end{Bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

$$[[C]_d \quad [C]_i] \begin{Bmatrix} \{c\}_d \\ \{c\}_i \end{Bmatrix} = \{d\}$$

$[C]_d$ is a square non-singular matrix and $\{c\}_d$ are the dependent coefficients that can be derived from the independent coefficients $\{c\}_i$:

$$\{c\}_d = [C]_d^{-1}(\{d\} - [C]_i \{c\}_i) \quad (18)$$

Substituting $\{c\}_d$ in (17) and removing $\{\lambda\}$ the following system is obtained to determine $\{c\}_i$:

$$([U]_s + \rho [V]_s) \{c\}_i = \{d_s\} \quad (19)$$

where:

$$[U]_s = ([U]_i - [U]_{di} [C]_d^{-1} [C]_i + [C]_i^T ([C]_d^T)^{-1} [U]_d [C]_d^{-1} [C]_i - [C]_i^T ([C]_d^T)^{-1} [U]_{id}) \quad (20)$$

$$[V_s] = ([V]_i - [V]_{di}[C]_d^{-1}[C]_i + [C]_i^T([C]_d^T)^{-1}[V]_d[C]_d^{-1}[C]_i - [C]_i^T([C]_d^T)^{-1}[V]_{id}) \quad (21)$$

$$\{d_s\} = \{T\}_i - [C]_i^T([C]_d^T)^{-1}\{T\}_d + [C]_i^T([C]_d^T)^{-1}([U]_d + \rho[V]_d)[C]_d^{-1}\{d\} - ([U]_{di} + \rho[V]_{di})[C]_d^{-1}\{d\} \quad (22)$$

The first two matrices ($[U_s]$ and $[V_s]$) correspond to the internal strain energy and potential energy matrices of the complete structure satisfying the imposed boundary conditions.

Although the method was initially developed to determine the buckling onset of stiffened panels, it can also be used to obtain the static deformation corresponding to the in-plane loads together with a uniform out-of-plane pressure applied to each panel. The previous linear system of equations (19) provides the solution to this bending problem.

The buckling onset of the structure is obtained from the indeterminate solution of this system, giving rise to an eigenvalue problem providing the buckling load level corresponding to each buckling mode (eigenvalues) and the corresponding buckling deflection shape (eigenvectors).

$$\det([U_s] + \rho[V_s]) = 0 \quad (23)$$

3 APPLICATION TO COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

The classical laminate theory (Ref [2]) is applied. The strain at any lay of the laminate can be expressed as the addition of the mid-plane strain and the curvature contribution:

$$\{\varepsilon\}_k = \{\varepsilon^o\} + \bar{z}_k\{\kappa\} \quad (24)$$

Where the mid-plane strain and the curvature can be expressed in terms of the displacements field as follows:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^o \\ \varepsilon_y^o \\ \gamma_{xy}^o \end{Bmatrix}_k = \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \end{Bmatrix} ; \quad \begin{Bmatrix} \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}_k = \begin{Bmatrix} -\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \\ -\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} \\ -2\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (25)$$

3.2 Strain Energy

The strain energy variation for a set of N composite plates stems from the next expression:

$$\delta U = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^N \int_0^{a_k} \int_0^{b_k} \left[\{\varepsilon^o\}_k^T [A]_k \{\varepsilon^o\}_k + 2\{\varepsilon^o\}_k^T [B]_k \{\kappa\}_k + \{\kappa\}_k^T [D]_k \{\kappa\}_k \right] dx dy \quad (26)$$

where the index k denotes the panel identification and [A], [B] and [D] are the laminate stiffness matrices according to the classical laminate theory.

Retaining the terms depending on the vertical displacements the following expression is derived for the strain energy variation:

$$\delta U = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^N \int_0^{a_k} \int_0^{b_k} \left[D_{11}^k \left(\frac{\partial^2 w_k}{\partial x^2} \right)^2 + D_{22}^k \left(\frac{\partial^2 w_k}{\partial y^2} \right)^2 + D_{33}^k \left(2 \frac{\partial^2 w_k}{\partial x \partial y} \right)^2 + 2D_{12}^k \frac{\partial^2 w_k}{\partial y^2} \frac{\partial^2 w_k}{\partial x^2} + 2D_{23}^k \frac{\partial^2 w_k}{\partial y^2} 2 \frac{\partial^2 w_k}{\partial x \partial y} + 2D_{13}^k \frac{\partial^2 w_k}{\partial x^2} \frac{\partial^2 w_k}{\partial x \partial y} \right] dx dy \quad (27)$$

When a plate contains stringers in longitudinal and/or transversal direction, the following terms must be added:

$$\delta U_{st} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^N \sum_{i=1}^{N_{stx}} \int_0^{a_k} EI_i^k \left(\frac{\partial^2 w_k}{\partial x^2} \right)^2 \Big|_{y=yst_i} dx + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^N \sum_{i=1}^{N_{sty}} \int_0^{b_k} EI_i^k \left(\frac{\partial^2 w_k}{\partial x^2} \right)^2 \Big|_{x=xst_i} dy \quad (28)$$

3.3 Potential energy of external loads

The potential energy variation corresponding to the configuration already described, stems from the next expression:

$$\partial V = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^N \int_0^{a_k} \int_0^{b_k} \left[N_x^k \left(\frac{\partial w_k}{\partial x} \right)^2 + N_y^k \left(\frac{\partial w_k}{\partial y} \right)^2 + 2N_{xy}^k \left(\frac{\partial w_k}{\partial x} \frac{\partial w_k}{\partial y} \right) + p^k w_k \right] dx dy \quad (29)$$

In order to account for the possible in-plane bending, the longitudinal and transverse flows can be also defined as Chebyshev series:

$$N_x^k = \sum_{m=0}^{n_x} N_x^{k,m} T_m(y), \quad N_y^k = \sum_{m=0}^{n_y} N_y^{k,m} T_m(x) \quad (30)$$

When a plate contains stringers in longitudinal and/or transversal direction, the following terms must be added:

$$\delta V_{st} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^N \sum_{i=1}^{N_{stx}} \int_0^{a_k} F_i^k \left(\frac{\partial w_k}{\partial x} \right)^2 \Big|_{y=yst_i} dx + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^{N_{sty}} \int_0^{b_k} F_j^k \left(\frac{\partial w_k}{\partial x} \right)^2 \Big|_{x=xst_j} dy \quad (31)$$

4 RESULTS

4.1 Single plates

In order to verify the correctness of the method, the result for a single panel subjected to different loading combinations and imposing different boundary conditions are compared against FE results (NASTRAN)

The following table summarizes the geometry and properties used.

Parameter	Units	Value
Ply thickness	mm	0.184
Layup	–	(45/-45/0/90)\$
Dimensions	mm x mm	250x320

Table 1: Single panel boundary conditions validation.

Figure 1: Plate under longitudinal load [simply supported($x=0, x=L, y=0, y=W$)]

Figure 2: Plate under longitudinal load [simply supported($x=0, x=L$), free($y=0, y=W$)]

Figure 3: Plate under longitudinal load [simply supported($x=0, x=L$), free($y=W$), clamped($y=0$)]

Figure 4: Plate under longitudinal load [simply supported($x=0, x=L$), continuity ($y=W$ & $y=0$)]

4.2 Stringer sections

Different stringer sections are assessed comparing the results with the ones from NASTRAN.

t	mm	0.184
Flanges layup	–	(45/-45/0/0/0/-45/45/90/0/0/0/0/90/-45/45/0/0/0/-45/45/0/0)
Web layup	–	(45/-45/0/0/0/-45/45/90/0/0/0/0/90/-45/45/0/0/0/-45/45/0/0)S
Length	mm	400
Attached flange width	mm	60
Web height	mm	45
Free flange width (I)	mm	60
Free flange width (C)	mm	18.75

Table 2: Stringer configuration.

	T section	I section	C section	Omega section
Rayleigh-Ritz				
	$N_{x,cr} = 5770$	$N_{x,cr} = 4735$	$N_{x,cr} = 5041$	$\lambda_{,cr} = 3.62$
NASTRAN				
	$N_{x,cr} = 5781$	$N_{x,cr} = 4736$	$N_{x,cr} = 5094$	$\lambda_{,cr} = 3.64$
	-0.19 %	-0.02 %	-1.04 %	-0.55 %

Figure 5: Stringer sections under longitudinal load (T, I and C) and pure shear (Omega)

4.4 Application to more general structures

To illustrate the wide range of applicability of the exposed method, a simplified torque box composed by 12 blade stringers and an omega stringer is assessed to obtain the local buckling of each segment of the assembly:

t	mm	0.184
Layup	–	(45/-45/0/90)\$
Box length	mm	500
Box height	mm	480
Box width	mm	960
Blades' height	mm	50
Omega height	mm	50
Omega cap width	mm	60

Table 4: Torque box configuration.

	MODE 1	MODE 2	MODE 3
Rayleigh-Ritz			
	$\epsilon_{x,cr} = 2065$	$\epsilon_{x,cr} = 2105$	$\epsilon_{x,cr} = 2256$
NASTRAN			
	$\epsilon_{x,cr} = 2047$	$\epsilon_{x,cr} = 2078$	$\epsilon_{x,cr} = 2229$
	0.9 %	1.3 %	1.2 %

Figure 6: Stringer sections under longitudinal load (T, I and C) and pure shear (Omega)

4.4 Unfolding moment in spar corner radius

The method described in this paper is also able to obtain, in addition to the buckling loads, the static deformation of the structure submitted to in-plane and out of plane pressure loads.

In fuel tank boxes, the internal pressure acts on spar and cover panels producing unfolding loads in the spar corner radius. Spar and Cover panels are submitted to in-plane loads in addition to the fuel pressure load. The interaction between these loads is non-linear and increases the unfolding bending moment. This non-linear effect is captured by the proposed method showing a good correlation in the unfolding moment with the DFEM results.

Figure 7: Cover and spar idealization used to obtain the unfolding moments

Figure 8: Unfolding moment for different load cases

The method proposed is able to obtain accurately the unfolding moment acting on the spar corner reducing the use of detailed finite element models.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The typical limitation of classical Rayleigh-Ritz methods, where a deflection shape function pre-satisfying the boundary conditions has to be used, can be removed by using the proposed method without penalizing the performance.

In addition to the definable boundary restrictions, compatibility conditions can also be defined between different panels, enlarging the scope of applicability from rectangular panels to more general assemblies composed by interconnected rectangular panels.

The proposed method has proved to be applicable to a wide range of different structures including from single plates to complete torque boxes, showing a good correlation against FE results ($\pm 3\%$).

The high performance of this approach based on the Rayleigh-Ritz method compared with more general FE methods (~ 10 times faster), makes it suitable to be used together with optimization engines.

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